

IMPACT STUDY OF THE COMMUNITY EXTENSION PROJECT: SOLAR ENERGY UTILIZATION SYSTEM OF LAGUNA STATE POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This paper aimed to assess the impact of the project named “Solar Energy Utilization System” of COE LSPU-SCC. This qualitative research used a guide questionnaire through text messages with the participants of the project. These objectives to meet: demographic profile of the respondents; impact assessment on the three domains: knowledge, skills, and acquired values/ attitude; services and activities conducted and level contribution in the performance of respondents’ duties and responsibilities and challenges encountered. There were five participants interviewed. The majority of the participants were 52 of age and 46. Male participants were married and some at college and vocational levels. It was concluded that the college extension program was highly beneficial to the participants specifically in reducing their electricity expenses at home. The knowledge, skills, and values acquired empowered the participants to gain a sense of duty and self-fulfillment that inspired them to make their living conditions better. The participants also became more empathic to the needs and concerns of the people around them especially those in their family and community. A successful collaboration between the Municipality of Majayjay, Laguna, and LSPU their services and activities were accomplished as reflected in the Memorandum of Agreement. It experienced different challenges along the planning, implementation, and monitoring phases of the project, project management committee, money involved as well as materials needed, the participants, and the venue. Full support of both parties to the community will be improved by evaluating the feedback and should have follow-up training for skills upgrading of the participants.

Keywords: *Challenges, Knowledge, Skills acquired, social output, self-fulfillment, values*

INTRODUCTION

In line with the university's vision of being a center of sustainable development initiatives transforming lives and communities, and its mission to provide quality education through instruction, research, and extension, the College of Engineering extension unit embarks on programs and projects for improved quality of life towards nation-building.

It is essential to conduct an impact assessment for programs and projects to be considered successful and worthy to be replicated. According to Canan and Hennessy (1985) social impact assessment as anticipatory research attempts to provide decision-makers with information about likely social outcome of adopting policy, instituting a program, or initiating a project that may impact the future.

According to the Guidelines and Principles for Social Impact Assessment prepared by The Interorganizational Committee on Guidelines and Principles for Social Impact Assessment, there are three ways in determining the social impact; such as, to predict (probable impact of the development), to go through a series of stages planning, implementation, and construction), and to understand the different variables (population characteristics, community and institutional structures etc.) (Inter-organizational Committee on Guidelines and Principles for Social Impact Assessment, May 1994).

The subject of this impact assessment is the extension project of the college extension unit entitled "Solar Energy Utilization System" birthed from Board Resolution No. 1357, S. 2017 under the approved program titled "Mula sa GAD Tulong Pang-abilidad para sa Mamamayan ng Majayjay, Laguna. The general objective of the project was to educate the community about alternative source of energy and the importance of using renewable energy. Knowledge gained allowed the beneficiaries to opt for an alternative resource to lessen their energy consumption.

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the training participants?
2. What is the extent and educational impact and effectiveness of the training to the respondents in terms of knowledge acquired, skills acquired, and acquired values/ attitude?
3. What are the services and activities conducted and the level of contribution in the performance of respondents' duties and responsibilities
4. What are the challenges encountered that hinder the success of the program including planning, implementation, and monitoring?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers used a qualitative research design, Creswell (2014) stated that qualitative research is an inquiry process of understanding based on distinct methodological traditions of inquiry that explore a social or human problem. The researchers build a complex, holistic picture, analyze words, report detailed views of information, and conduct the study in a natural setting.

A deductive approach was used to interpret the answers of the participants. According to Bingham & Witkowsky (2022) a deductive approach is a kind of “top-down” approach to data analysis. This involves analyzing qualitative data based on a structure that is predetermined the researcher. This is because the answers that the researcher is going to receive from the sample population is anticipated.

The researchers asked questions through text messages because of the pandemic situations. The proponents ask the demographic profile of the trainees like, Age, Sex, Civil Status, Educational Background and Employment Status. Additionally, some questions ask “Naging Mahalaga ba ang training na ito sa iyo?”, “May natutunan ka bas a training na ito?”, “Ano ang nabago sa ugali at pananaw mo sa buhay?”, “Kumikita sa nangyaring training na ito?”, “May Negosyo ka bang pwedeng gawin?”, and “Pwede mo bang irekomenda sa iba ang training na ito?”. Assessing the different challenges encountered along planning, implementation and monitoring of Extension services.

Below is the implementation flow of the extension services including the community outcome assessment, the LGU coordination next is Community needs assessment then needs based program design then education training, the post intervention and outcomes survey. The process flow for the development and implementation of extension program is presented below in Figure 1 (Llenares et al 2017).

Research Locale

The research focused on trainees from the different Barangays in the Municipality of Majayjay, Laguna.

Population and Design

The number of samples is composed of 5 participants or trainees who were able to participate through the exchange of texts since this was done during the pandemic and physical meetings were very limited.

Figure 1 Implementation flow of the COE extension project

RESULTS

Demographic Profile

Table 1. Profile of the Participants

Participants Background	Age	Sex	Civil Status	Educational
1	46	M	M	College level
2	52	M	M	College level
3	52	M	M	College Graduate
4	46	M	M	Secondary level
5	34	F	S	Vocational

Table 1 shows the profile of the trainees (participants) as to age, sex, civil status and educational background. Majority were Male and Married and aged 30 and above. Some of them were college level who has a background in electricity.

Table 2. Impact Assessment

Knowledge Acquired	Question No. 2. “May natutunan ka ba sa training na ito?”
Skills Acquired ito?”	Question No. 4. “Kumikita ba ko sa nangyaring training na Question No. 5. “May Negosyo ka bang pwedeng gawin?”
Values Attitude Acquired iyo?”	Question No. 1. “Naging Mahalaga ba ang training na ito sa Question No. 3. “Ano ang nabago sa ugali at pananaw mo sa buhay?” Question No. 6. “Pwede mo bang irekomenda sa iba ang training na ito?”.

Interview with the Participants

Question No. 1. “Naging Mahalaga ba ang training na ito sa iyo?”

Replies

Trainee 1: “Napakahalaga ng training na ito para sa akin dahil makadaragdag ito ng bagong kaalaman na magagamit ko sa kapakinabangan di lamang sa pansarili kundi maging sa iba”

Trainee 2: “Para magkaroon ng karagdagang kaalaman at magamit sa pagtrabaho.”

Trainee 3: “Dahil po dito nadagdagan ang aking kaalaman bilang isang Electronics technician”

Trainee 4: “Napakahalaga ng training na ito hindi lng dahil nadagdagan ang aking kaalaman nakatulong pa ako sa pamilya ko”

Trainee 5: “Nadagdagan pa akung kaalaman at magkaroon ng kaibigan”

Question No. 2. “May natutunan ka bas a training na ito?”

Replies:

Trainee 1: “Ang natutunan ko sa training na ito ay kung paano makabasa at makagawa ng circuit diagram na susuplayan ng kuryente mula sa sinag ng araw at ang mga kagamitan at materyales para dito sa ganito nadagdagan ang skills ko na pwede kong maishare sa iba.”

Trainee 2: “Ang natutunan ko ay ang pagcoconnect ng solar system pero hindi ko pa po nashashare”

Trainee 3: *“Napakahalaga po sa akin na matutunan ang tamang mga paraan at kagamitan para sap ag iinstilasyon ng isang solar system lalong lalo na napakamahal ng ating ibinibayad sa ating electric bill”*

Trainee 4: *“Yes naman po. Dito nalaman ko ang lahat ng materyales mula sa pinakamaliit hanggang sa pinakamalaki. Ika nga nila hindi maloloko rito ang tamanag paglilinya at pagpapatakbo ng isang solar project. Pati na rin ang pagwiwiring ng kuryente na syang nagung daan para lubos kong maintindihan ang takbo ng electrisidad ng bawat tahanan”*

Trainee 5: *“Marami po at nagbago ang aking pananaw sa buhay na kahit babae lng ako kaya ko pala, di ko lng maishare pa sa iba at pandemic”*

Question No. 3. *“Ano ang nabago sa ugali at pananaw mo sa buhay?”*

Replies:

Trainee 1: *“Nabago nito ang ugali at pananaw ko sa buhay sapagkat sa natutunan ko proud ako sa sarili dahil sa bagong kakayanan na pwede ong magamit saan man at kung kinakailangan.”*

Trainee 2: *“Opo nabago din naman po dahil sa training”*

Trainee 3: *“Sa pagkakataong ito maipagmamalaki ko ang aking sarili na di napagiiwanan ng iba na may kaalaman na sa larangan ng solar”*

Trainee 4: *“Napakalaki ng iniambag nito upang mabago ang aking paguugaliat pananaw, una rito nagging proud ako dahil ako na mismo ay nakagagawa ng mga bagay na madalas itinatawag pa natin o ibinabayad pa natin sa ibang tao para trabahuhin o ayusin”*

Trainee 5: *“Opo nagbago nman po ako kaso nag lock down”*

Question No. 4. *“Kumikita ba ko sa nangyaring training na ito?”*

Replies:

Trainee 1: *“ Bagamat di pa nadaragdagan ang kita ko sa ngayon pero sa katagalan ay makakatipid naman sa bayarin sa electric bill”*

Trainee 2: *“Hindi pa po dahil po sa pandemic”*

Trainee 3: *“Dahil sa seminar naibahagi nila sa amin ang tamang paraan at maibabahagi din sa iba”*

Trainee 4: *“Maaring sa ngayon hindi pa ako kumikita pero dahil naiapply ko naman ito sa sarili naming tahanan nabawasan naman ang aming gastusin”*

Trainee 5: *“Di pa po nadagdagan kc gawa ng pandemic kaya di ko pa masyado naishare at walang kagamitan”*

Question No. 5. *“May Negosyo ka bang pwedeng gawin?”*

Replies:

Trainee 1: *“Mayroon akong naisip na negosyo mula sa training na ito ay ang supply and installation of materials. Malaki ang naudulot ng training dahil magagamit ito panghanapbuhay”*

Trainee 2: *“Meron na pong naisip na Negosyo pero kapos pa rin po sa budget”*

Trainee 3: *“Di pa man napapanahon na nakadagdag ito sa aking kinikita dahil sa kakulangan pinasyal pinapangarap ko na makapagtayo ng sariling Solar System Repair Shop and installation dito sa aking bayang sinilangan”.*

Trainee 4: *“Nang dahil sa dagdag kaalaman na aking natutunan nagkaroon ako ng lakas ng loob na makipag usap sa mga dealer ng solar equipment at isa ito sa pinagkaka abalahan ko”*

Trainee 5: *“Meron na po sana akong baka pagkatapos ng pandemic kaya di ko pa masyado maishare at wala pa kagamitan”*

Question No. 6. *“Pwede mo bang irekomenda sa iba ang training na ito?”.*

Replies:

Trainee 1: *“Nais kong irekomenda ang training na ito para sa iba nang sa ganun ay maging kataulad ko rin sila na natuto at naranasan ang kapakinabangang dulot nito.”*

Trainee 2: *“Oo naman po syempre para maishare din po ang natutunan naming sa solar”*

Trainee 3: *“Mithiin ko sa darating na panahon bilang nagging kagawad ng barangay ng pitong taon gusto kong makatulong sa aking mga kababayan na maibahagi ko ang aking natutunan sa aking mga kababayan na may interest na matuto sa larangan ng electronics lalo na sa solar system application”*

Trainee 4: *“Highly recommended ko po ang training na ito hindi lng pampamilya pang Negosyo pa.”*

Trainee 5: *“Opo gusto ko sana naishare ang aking mga natutunan sa training”*

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the profile of the trainees (participants) as to age, sex, civil status and educational background. Majority were Male and Married and aged 30 and above. Some of them were college level who has a background in electricity.

Knowledge Acquired

The respondents replied positively when asked about the knowledge they have acquired from the training. Meeting the objectives of the project, respondents learned how to read and create a circuit diagram of a solar panel, the materials needed, and electrical wiring. Basic knowledge of solar panel installation was important to the respondents especially since electric costs were increasing. According to Calixto (2024) the study emphasizes the importance of executing a comprehensive community development plan to address the identified needs of the barangays, ultimately aiming to enhance the quality of life for residents in these communities.

Skills Acquired

One objective of the project is for the participants to be able to apply the skills acquired as a livelihood. Although some of the respondents were not yet able to use the skills to generate income because of the pandemic, the majority of them shared that their expenses in electricity were lessened. Participant were able to apply the skills they acquired in their own respective households. The respondents was also able to think of possible businesses they can start from the skills they acquired. One answered, the supply and installation of materials, and the other answered a solar panel repair shop and installation. One respondent even started negotiating with solar equipment dealers. Salazar (2020) mentioned that social impacts measure how the lives of the recipients of extension programs were benefited in terms of productivity and further developed them into more self-reliant and decisive residents with the objective of honing them to become socially responsive people of the country.

Values/ Attitudes Acquired

Considering the answers of the respondents, the majority of them see their learning as something they can share with their family and members of the community where they belong to. The training did not only serve as additional knowledge and skills but also inspired them to share to others. They also value the kinship experienced through the training. The learnings they had made them proud of themselves because they know that the skills and knowledge, they gained may be used to help others. This gave the

respondents a sense of duty and self-fulfilment. The respondents answered they want to recommend the training to others so they can experience the learnings they had. Basic competencies contribute to the improvement of the softskills of the students, such as communication, teamwork, confidence, and the like, while the common and core competencies contribute to the technical skills necessary for the trainees to be learned (Terano, 2023).

Services and activities conducted and level of contribution in the performance of respondents' duties and responsibilities

The LGU was in charged in the selection of participants, the venue and food needed by the faculty, facilitator and participants. The material requirements for the said training were approved by the BOR. The other electrical tools needed in the workshop was brought by the participants since it will be beneficial for them in the future purposes after the training. The participants also help their co participants during the workshop to learn more after the assistance of all the facilitators and the Trainor. The selected BSEE students also help the participants during the workshop for the easy facilitation. It was also discussed the maintenance procedure in "Solar Utilization System".

Challenges encountered along planning, implementation and monitoring

One of the challenges is the uncontrollable variables like the environment and climate. Although, the environment on that particular training days were friendly and sometimes there were times of little rain shower, but we still tried to continue the training. The school vehicle was not available on the second up to the fourth day of the training. It was very challenging for the faculty to go to the venue in Majajay, Laguna and it was very obvious of the very mountainous and a distant place from LSPU. The budget for the materials was charged to LSPU while LGU was in charge for the food of the faculty and students. The faculty members in charge were not all available seeing that they have scheduled class on that day. A few participants sometimes did not finish the training because of personal issues, especially the female participants. Moreover, in monitoring during this time of pandemic, reaching out to other participants personally was a very challenging task due to limited physical engagements.

A public involvement and conflict management program can beneficially be closely integrated with the development of the social impact assessment process. A lack of understanding still exists among many decision-makers as to how public involvement fit within the planning process. Public involvement can complement and fit within SIA process by identifying potentially affected groups, and by interpreting the meaning of impacts for each group. Public involvement plays an important role in recruiting participants for the planning process who are truly representative of affected groups. Public involvement should be truly interactive, with communication flowing both ways between the agency and affected groups (Guidelines and Principles for Social Impact Assessment 1994).

Conclusions

Generally, based from the results of the assessment and interview, it can be concluded that the college extension program was highly beneficial to the participants specifically in reducing their electricity expenses at home. The knowledge, skills, and values acquired empowered the participants to gain a sense of duty and self-fulfilment that inspired them to make their living conditions better. The participants also became more empathic to the needs and concerns of the people around them especially those in their family and community. However, the school needs to do something for the community to fully benefit the programs and projects. Linkages and partnerships with other agencies are suggested to attain project sustainability and more desirable outcomes (Olavides et al 2019).

Recommendations

With the aforementioned conclusions, the following recommendations are formed, these are: (1) the college extension unit may conduct another similar project to other communities with larger number of participants if possible. (2) one limit encountered by the participant is the lack of budget for materials to turn their skills into a livelihood, so it is suggested that a separate starter kit after the program may be granted to outstanding participants if not possible to all (3) for the internal factors that challenged the extensionists during the course of the training, better coordination must be done to ensure availability of resources such as logistics; faculty members in charge must also be given ample time to handle both instruction and extension responsibilities effectively. Montalbo (2016) stated that the results might be used in continuing the programs since they strengthen the development of the beneficiaries using needs assessment as the basis for program implementation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers uphold that this study was conducted in accordance with rigorous ethical standards, guaranteeing that all respondents provided informed consent and were also permitted to disengage from the study at any phase. Respondent anonymity was meticulously preserved to ensure their privacy, and their welfare was prioritized throughout the research process.

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